

OPTICAL FIBER SENSORS TO SENSE DELAMINATION GROWTH IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

One of the prevalent damage modes in laminated composite structures is the propagation of delaminations from free-edges, cutouts, tapered cross-sections, or generally any type of geometric discontinuity. Optical fiber sensors are uniquely suited to sensing such delaminations in that they can be embedded in the laminate, e.g., between plies, and used to sense the strain field associated with delamination. A finite element (FE) model of an axially loaded $[0,90]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminate is utilized to relate perturbations in the transverse strain field, caused by a free-edge delamination, to effects on an embedded optical fiber sensor. The sensor is modeled as a resin-rich region surrounding a protective coating, cladding and an optical fiber core. Analytical results demonstrate that the transverse strain near the optical fiber sensor increases in proportion to the delamination size. Based on measured transverse strain sensitivity of selected optical fiber sensors, it is noteworthy that changes in the analytically predicted strains are significant enough to be detected by the sensor. Rudimentary experimental results support this hypothesis.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, significant effort has been focused on the development of structurally efficient laminated composite structures. Since these advanced materials exhibit structural behavior significantly different than that of their monolithic counterparts, new non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods of assessing structural integrity are essential to the growth of composites applications. Several methods of examining composite structures have been utilized, e.g., x-radiography, ultrasound, and infrared thermography. However, none of these assessment methods can be readily implemented while the part to be inspected is in service. Oftentimes, due to the complexity and size of some composite structures, parts may be extracted from the main structure for NDE. One of the interesting solutions appropriate for the NDE of a composite structure may be to embed optical fiber sensors in the structure, e.g., between the plies at predetermined critical locations. Such sensors must be of small dimension in order not to disrupt or to hinder the overall structure. Note that the dimensions of an optical fiber can range from 60 - 125 μm in diameter, whereas the ply thickness of a laminated composite is on the order of 75 - 200 μm . With these dimensional relationships, it has been shown that embedded optical fibers do not necessarily degrade the macroscopic properties of laminated composites¹. Other advantages of using optical fiber sensors relate to their strain sensitivity, high temperature resistance, geometric versatility, immunity to electromagnetic interference, electrical isolation, and real-time sensing capability.

Composite structures have an advantage over metals in higher strength-to-weight ratios; however, they exhibit a much more complex set of failure modes in service. One of the most common and perplexing failure modes is denoted "free-edge delamination", and is caused by the existence of a complex stress state in the vicinity of the free-edge. More generally, these stresses may occur near cut-outs, joints, tapered geometries, etc. Frequently, the out-of-plane stresses for these geometries are the primary cause of the initiation and propagation of delamination².

Optical Fiber Sensor Overview

Optical fibers are primarily designed and utilized for telecommunication applications. Currently there is a great interest in utilizing optical fibers as sensors because of their availability and desirable properties. Due to their rugged design, these fibers are not very sensitive to external perturbations. Consequently, modifications to the protective coating are required to make the telecommunication fiber more sensitive to external loads. A major advantage to such modified sensors is the capability to measure small strain fields. For example, it has been reported that a Mach-Zender fiber optic interferometer can detect phase differences on the order of 1 micro-radian of light which is equivalent to 10^{-13} meters³.

Optical fibers may be configured into different architectures to sense strain, force and temperature with a range of sensitivities. Fiber sensors can be broadly classified into two groups, interferometric and intensity based⁴. The interferometric sensors utilize the coherent addition of two optical beams propagating in two fibers (Mach-Zender or Michaelson sensors) or in a single fiber (Fabry-Perot, Polarimetric sensors). The strain changes the relative phase between the two beams and thus the intensity at the output of the sensor where the beams are combined. These sensors are very sensitive since a length change of half a wavelength of light, approximately $0.3 \mu\text{m}$, is enough to change the output light intensity from a maximum to a minimum. These sensors are sensitive both to axial as well as transverse (radial) strain.

Intensity based sensors that have been used in composites include microbend and macrobend sensors. In these sensors, light is lost from the fiber core when either transverse forces (microbend) or strain changes affecting the bend radius of the fiber (macrobend) are present. Intensity based sensor systems are typically simpler than the interferometric systems, but are much less sensitive.

Optical Fibers Embedded in Laminate

The presence of an optical fiber in a laminated composite structure increases the complexity of the constituent microstructure. A resin rich area surrounds the fiber; its shape and interface characteristics are dependent on both fiber orientation and processing conditions. Structural complexity is also associated with the ingress/egress locations of the optical fiber. While optical fibers have been shown to enhance the tensile strength of laminates¹, the resin rich area surrounding optical fibers can be the initiation site for delamination⁵. The effect of embedding optical fibers in laminated composites is, therefore, very complex and not fully understood.

In order to enhance the sensitivity of embedded optical fiber sensors, several properties of the constituents of the composite material and the optical fiber must be quantified. Firstly, the level of sensitivity of an optical sensor is strongly dependent upon the elastic moduli of the resin rich area and the optical fiber coating⁶. A proper selection of optical fiber and coating can increase the sensitivity by 10-100 times that of the bare fiber^{7,8}. The optical fiber used in the referenced studies was an acrylate coated optical fiber. The modulus of elasticity for this coating is lower than that of some commercially available coated fibers, e.g., aluminum, gold, polyimide. Secondly, the placement of the optical sensor can further enhance the sensitivity for accurate strain measurement

along the sensor⁹. Voids that can occur along an embedded sensor can be problematic¹⁰, in that this leads to a degradation in load transfer between the sensor and the surrounding resin. The occurrence of such defects can be avoided by proper control of temperature and pressure during the curing process of laminates with embedded sensors.

NUMERICAL MODEL

Finite element models have been utilized in these efforts to study the localized strain(stress) field in the vicinity of an optical fiber sensor. Interest has been particularly focused on the transverse strains produced near the free-edge of laminates subjected to in-plane axial loads. A university version of an industry standard FE code (ANSYS¹¹) has been utilized to obtain all of the results. The FE models include a representation of the sensor, i.e., resin-rich region, protective coating, cladding and optical fiber core; in addition, interlaminar cracks (delaminations) can be represented at predefined interfaces. The laminate geometry studied here has been a $[0,90]_s$ graphite/epoxy which has high interlaminar stresses near the free-edge when subjected to in-plane axial loads. For the purpose of sensing these transverse stresses (or strains), an optical fiber sensor is located at the midplane and near the free-edge of each of the FE models studied. A total of nine separate cases have been modeled and evaluated. These models include two baseline models with no delaminations, one with and one without a sensor. The latter case was simply for initial verification of the model. The remaining six cases involve different delamination lengths of one, two and three ply thicknesses, at either the midplane or at the $[0,90]$ interface. Numerical results are compared to the FE results of Wang and Crossman², elasticity results of Pipes and Pagano¹², and the FE results of Fuehne and Engblom¹³ to verify the model's accuracy.

The FE model represents a cross-sectional quadrant of a straight-sided tensile specimen. Important dimensions of the model include the height-to-width ratio, $h/b = 0.25$, where $h = 2t$ and $b = 8t$; and t is the ply thickness. The layer thickness is specified as 0.10 inches. Herein, a layer denotes a subset of adjacent plies of equal fiber orientation. Figure 1 displays a typical FE mesh for the $[0,90]_s$ laminate with the embedded sensor mesh, i.e., including the optical fiber, coating and resin-rich region; the sensor being located at the laminate midplane and near the free-edge. The complete FE model is divided into three levels of mesh refinement including a fine mesh near the free-edge with element size of 0.10 inches (square). The medium and coarse meshes have element sizes of 0.02 x 0.01 inches and 0.04 x 0.01 inches, respectively. The FE models are comprised of 980 (3D, 8 noded isoparametric) elements.

The optical sensor model has been represented as having an outer coating diameter of 0.00512 inches (125 μm), and a cladding diameter of 0.00433 inches (110 μm). The optical fiber is oriented in the longitudinal direction, at the midplane of the laminate model and at 1 layer thickness from the free-edge ($Y/b = 0.75$). Since the optical fiber is aligned with the longitudinal X axis and the adjacent composite plies are perpendicular to the optical fiber, a resin rich area is created and is assumed to be approximately 5 times the diameter of the optical fiber. This assumption was based on experience gained in the fabrication of test specimens.

Each ply in the model has been represented by the unidirectional graphite/epoxy material properties given below

$$E_L = 20 \text{ Mpsi}; E_T = E_Z = 2.1 \text{ Mpsi}; G_{LT} = G_{LZ} = G_{TZ} = 0.85 \text{ Mpsi}; \nu_{LT} = \nu_{LZ} = \nu_{TZ} = 0.21$$

where the subscripts L, T, and Z represent the longitudinal, transverse and through-the-thickness directions, respectively. Note that the term E_I is the extensional modulus in the I^{TH} direction; G_{IJ} is the shear modulus in the IJ^{TH} plane; and the ν_{ij} terms represent the major Poisson's ratios in the

IJ planes. Material properties assumed for the optical sensor system¹⁴ are defined as

$$E_{\text{CORE}} = E_{\text{CLADDING}} = 10.3 \text{ Mpsi}; E_{\text{COATING}} = 0.50 \text{ Mpsi}; E_{\text{RESIN-RICH}} = 0.25 \text{ Mpsi}$$

$$\nu_{\text{CORE}} = \nu_{\text{CLADDING}} = 0.14; \nu_{\text{COATING}} = 0.34; \nu_{\text{RESIN-RICH}} = 0.35$$

Since the core and cladding have the same mechanical properties but different indices of refraction, the model utilizes one set of mechanical properties for the core/cladding combination. The polyimide coated fiber modeled in this study was found to produce the highest sensitivity when compared to acrylate coatings and to bare fibers¹⁴. Thus the interest in this type of coated sensor.

The sensor model contains several regions of differing shape and material properties. Care has been taken to assure good nodal connectivity between the optical fiber and resin-rich area, see Figure 1. The laminate model consists of two symmetric layers, where the upper layer has fibers aligned in the longitudinal (loading) 0° direction, and the lower layer has fibers aligned in the transverse (across-the-load) 90° direction. The lower layer mesh has a cavity to accommodate inclusion of the sensor model, as shown in Figure 1. The overall model, i.e., with optical sensor, has been constrained to provide symmetry in the midplane (XY plane) and along the centerline of the tensile loaded configuration (XZ plane).

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Finite element results have been compared with other finite element and elasticity results for the free-edge problem both with and without a delamination. While these results are generally discussed below, only limited verification results are presented here. Additionally, the most relevant effects of delamination growth are given in the form of transverse strain variation (at the sensor) vs. delamination size(length).

Model Verification

The finite element model is displaced longitudinally (tension) an amount $1 \mu\epsilon$ to correspond to results obtained in^{2,12,13}. Note that the mesh refinement near the free-edge is not as fine as that in Wang and Crossman². While not presented here, some studies with more refined meshes did not significantly alter the stress/strain predictions. All of the results are given, therefore, for the model with 10 elements per layer, i.e., through-the-thickness of the laminate. Variation in interlaminar shear stress τ_{yz} and interlaminar normal stress σ_z have been determined at the midplane and at the [0,90] interface. These stress variations are in good agreement with those obtained by finite element and elasticity methods^{2,12}. Even for the more complex case with a free-edge delamination included, these interlaminar stress variations compare very favorably to those obtained by Fuehne and Engblom¹³, e.g., as shown in Figure 2.

Delamination Effects at Sensor

The effect of the delamination on the optical fiber is to cause the cross-sectional area and dimension of the optical fiber to change as a function of the delamination size and location. Two models, midplane and [0,90] interface delamination, and four delamination sizes - 5, 10, 15, and 20 elements have been studied. Changes in sensor geometry would cause attenuation in the sensor and, depending on the type of sensor, would result in polarization, intensity, amplitude, phase or wavelength modulation. A predefined optical pattern/signature could be related to the strain which in turn relates to the delamination size/location. In determining changes in the cross-sectional area of the sensor, it is assumed that the fiber deforms symmetrically along major axes and into an

elliptical shape. Strain results have been obtained from the model in the principal axes, i.e., Y and Z axes. The cross-sectional area of the sensor has been calculated on the basis of changes in the major and minor axes with respect to the initial area. Results for these axially loaded cases indicate that the shear strain at the optical sensor is insignificant relative to the normal strain. In fact, the through-the-thickness normal strain ϵ_z is the primary contributor to the maximum transverse strain. Variation in the normal strains at the centerline of the embedded optical sensor, located at a distance from the free-edge of $Y/b = 0.75$, are presented in Figures 3 and 4 for the midplane and [0,90] interface delaminations, respectively. These results indicate how the transverse strains in the sensor vary as the delamination grows. In each of these cases, it is clear that the interlaminar normal strain ϵ_z dominates. For the midplane delamination, the maximum transverse strain, at the sensor, is predicted to vary on the order of 5% with the delamination growth. With the [0,90] interface delamination, a more distinct change in the maximum transverse strain at the sensor is predicted, i.e., on the order of 13%. Note that the transverse strains at the sensor are quite small in these studies because the enforced axial strain is small, actually $1 \mu\epsilon$.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A tip-loaded cantilever beam with a surface mounted single-mode (SM), optical-fiber sensor has been used to determine the feasibility of SM sensors for transverse strain measurements. These sensors are of the polarimetric type with birefringence induced by the strain field. The sensor was bonded perpendicular to the length and on the surface of an aluminum beam, as represented in the inset of Figure 5. The beam had an aspect ratio (length/depth) of approximately 150. An oscilloscope served to measure the maximum intensity in μW for a sequence of statically displaced positions of the cantilever beam. Figure 5 shows the characteristics of the output intensity of the sensor vs. the surface strain at the fiber. Note that the surface strain at the sensor is simply presumed to be equal to the elastic strain in the upper surface of the aluminum beam. The surface strain experienced by the optical sensor in this experiment can be approximately related to the transverse strain in a sensor embedded in a laminated composite. In each case, the transverse load changes the cross-sectional area of the sensor which in turn alters the sensors output intensity.

The transverse strain values attained in this experiment are relatively high compared to those calculated for the axially-loaded finite element models. Experimental strains were computed to be on the order of $100 \mu\epsilon$ while those for the FE models were at the $1 \mu\epsilon$ level. Even with a 100 fold increase in the axial strain for the FE model, the axial load applied to the laminate would be very reasonable, i.e., something that could easily be achievable in experiment. These results strongly indicate that the SM optical-sensor-system used in this cantilever beam experiment would have adequate sensitivity for detecting changes in the free-edge transverse strain effects in axially loaded laminated composite structures.

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Figure 1. Complete Finite Element Model, Including Optical Sensor, $[0/90]_8$ Laminate

Figure 2. Normal Stress σ_z Along $[0/90]$ Interface of $[0/90]_8$ Graphite Epoxy Laminate, Axial Load, Free-Edge Delamination With Length of One Ply Thickness

Figure 3. Transverse Strain Variation at Optical Sensor vs. Free-Edge (Midplane) Delamination Size

Figure 4. Transverse Strain Variation at Optical Sensor vs. Free-Edge (Interface) Delamination Size

Figure 5. Experimental Results, Output Intensity of Sensor vs. Surface Strain, for Cantilever Beam With Surface Bonded Single-Mode Optical Sensor